

FEATURES OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-DETERMINATION AMONG STUDENTS FROM DIFFERENT FIELDS AND THEIR CONNECTION WITH ALTRUISTIC ATTITUDES

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In today's world of rapid scientific and technological development, more and more people are thinking about professional self-fulfillment that will match their aspirations in terms of their abilities. Each profession requires certain personal qualities that are either innate or developed during the process of professional development.

Are there really differences between the manifestations of personality traits related to one type of profession or another in everyday life? We want to examine the manifestation of differences using the example of altruism.

Can we assume that a person's specific personality orientation, for example, “people-oriented,” is associated with a strong desire to help people, or is the line between types of professions blurred after all?

The world of professions and ways of self-determination are changing rapidly, and information is becoming insufficient. Every day, new professions appear as a result of constant technological progress, changes in working conditions, and the inconsistency of the previous content of work with the content of the same profession in the present [3]. Therefore, the question of the classification of professions is very acute.

First, it is necessary to define the concept of a profession. The term “profession” can be defined in four areas:

1. A profession is a field of work whose end result is the creation of certain products that have consumer value.
2. A profession is defined as a process of labor activity.
3. A profession determines the level of competence of an employee and also indicates their qualifications.
4. A profession determines the professional identity of each person as a special belonging to a group of people united by professional identity [4].

The question arises: how to choose a profession? We can use the “golden rule” of occupational psychology - “the best mutual correspondence - mutual compatibility - of a person as a subject of labor, on the one hand, and the objective requirements of a socially fixed job position, on the other” [4, p. 91].

According to A.N. Leontiev, activity is a system with its own structure, transformations, and internal transitions.

"In the general flow of activity that forms human life in its highest manifestations, mediated by psychological reflection, analysis distinguishes, first, individual [special] activities according to the criterion of their motivating motives. Next, actions are distinguished - processes that are subject to conscious goals. Finally, operations that directly depend on the conditions for achieving a specific goal. These “units” of human activity form its macrostructure. The

peculiarities of the analysis that leads to their identification consist in the fact that it does not use the division of living activity into elements, but reveals the internal relationships that characterize it." [7, p. 52].

Due to the process of technological development, there are more and more professions in which there is no “pure” type of profession. The same profession may require an employee to have knowledge of both computer programs and medicine. This is evidenced by a case described by J. Groopman: during a session with a doctor, the latter stops the patient at the 18-second mark of the patient's description of symptoms and complaints and establishes a treatment program based on indicators provided by a computer [2].

Let us consider E.A. Klimov's classification. This classification was created for career guidance work with schoolchildren, but differed in that it included key characteristics of professions corresponding to future professional activities. The type of perception of the world occurs individually, also due to professional activity. After analyzing the description of professions and the subject relevance of the characteristics of professionals, E.A. Klimov made the following conclusions: the images of the surrounding world differ, the division of social objects varies depending on the profession, the type of profession also affects the perception and differentiation of objects, and professionals have their own subjective world [5].

E.A. Klimov notes: "... When classifying professions into different types, one can take into account the most specific characteristics of professional activity or competence, the main functions of a professional in their work, or the functions that require the most extensive and sophisticated special education" [5, p. 58].

Work activity has its own varieties due to the objects with which a person interacts. Objects can be of the following types: natural [living and non-living nature], technical, social [groups and people], symbolic systems [language, formulas, systems of notation], artistic images.

The “person-person” type of profession works with social systems, communities, and people of different genders and ages. People with this type of profession teach, manage, work as medical professionals, and are more likely to provide services.

The “human-nature” type of profession works with plant organisms, animal organisms, and microorganisms. People in these professions may conduct research, engage in agriculture, or work in the food industry.

The “human-technology” type of profession works with mechanisms, machines, and their properties. This includes professions related to the repair, construction, production, and assembly of devices.

The “human-sign” type of profession works with signs and numbers, i.e., elements that carry a second symbolic level. These workers find it easier to process documents, numbers, and information in the form of diagrams and texts.

The “human-artistic image” type of profession works with elements of art and creativity. Work related to visual arts, music, literature, and acting.

Daniel Batson offers the following conceptualization: “Altruism is a motivational state whose ultimate goal is to increase the well-being of another person.” This definition includes three meanings [1].

The connection between empathy and altruism. In a study by Lavericheva, the influence of empathy on the manifestations of altruism and egoism was examined. The manifestation of altruistic behavior consisted in being able or unable to feel and perceive the state of another

person and the ability to understand that state. In other words, altruism is possible if one has the ability to “think” like an altruist [6]. Consequently, if we act altruistically, the act of behavior is preceded by a primary perception of the person (measured by a human sensitivity scale) and followed by an empathic process. The following results were identified during the study Respondents with low human sensitivity scores were more likely to be selfish. No direct correlation between human sensitivity and altruism was found. We assume that altruistic attitudes are more pronounced in people with “people-oriented” professions.

Our study was conducted at the Tashkent branch of Lomonosov Moscow State University. Students from four faculties participated in the study: Psychology, Applied Mathematics and Computer Science, Philology, and Management, from various courses, aged 18 to 25. The total number of respondents was 132.

Research methods:

1. M.I. Yasin's method - measurement of altruistic attitudes.
2. E.A. Klimov's method “Determining the type of future profession.”

At the first stage of the research, we needed to confirm the type of profession. The following types of professions were identified at the faculties:

	Psychology	AMCS	Management	Philology
p-human	18	10	7	6
p-sign	8	12	2	8
p-nature	10	2	0	3
p-artistic image	11	9	0	4
p-technology	0	4	0	0
Mixed	12	2	1	3

For comparison of altruistic attitudes, “pure types” were taken, i.e., a combination of career choice and confirmation of type by methodology.

	Asymp. significance [two-tailed]	Person-person	Person-sign
Altruism	0.799	21	20

According to the Mann-Whitney test, we see that there are no significant differences between the groups.

Our assumption about the relationship between profession type and altruistic attitudes was not confirmed.

In modern conditions, every employee must have skills corresponding to the “person-person” and “person-sign” types, since our life, on the one hand, is not separated from the computer [world of symbols], and on the other hand, the automation of production processes and the desire to increase earnings by working in the service sector or, for example, if a person is an agronomist [human-nature], but chooses to sell their products independently, focusing on people, then they tend to some extent to “become” a person with a “human-human” personality orientation; this phenomenon inclines people to combine types of professions.

Our results are obtained in connection with scientific and technological progress and changes in the requirements for the personal organization of representatives of certain professions. If this is the case, then the tools we have chosen are also somewhat inconsistent with the changes in the external environment that have taken place over the past few decades, which

can be conditionally called a new reality and which should definitely be studied at a deeper scientific and methodological level.

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